

Using case-based learning for nursing students: Integration techniques from a nursing lecturer's perspective

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This study investigated the potential of case-based learning (CBL) integration in English education to enhance nurse communication. Recognizing the relevance of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses to nursing, this research explores the application of CBL as a bridge between theoretical knowledge and practical communication skills. The qualitative research methods focused on one lecturer, a class, and 15 students. Data collection included observations and document analysis to better understand CBL implementation and outcomes. Preliminary findings indicated CBL alignment with established frameworks, involving case introduction, source analysis, group discussions, role-play, feedback, and reflection. It was concluded that, by adopting case-based learning, nursing education can equip future professionals with the language mastery that is essential for impactful patient interactions and collaborative care. The findings of this study provide insights into a practical methodology for enhancing nurse communication and English skills.

Keywords: Case-Based Learning; English for Specific Purpose; English for Nursing; Communication Skills

1. Introduction

In today's ever-evolving healthcare landscape, the significance of English proficiency for nurses cannot be overstated. English proficiency has become a vital requirement for nursing professionals, necessitating its integration into nursing education. This urgency is emphasized by Pradana et al. (2022), who identified nursing as an essential skill set mandated by ASEAN countries between 2015 and 2030. Consequently, nurses must prepare for international roles where effective cross-border communication is paramount. Boshier (2012) outlined the essential nature of nursing skills and stressed the need for

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nurses to possess a diverse skill set. These encompass (a) adept interviewing for information gathering, (b) therapeutic communication to guide patients through challenges, and (c) assertiveness to navigate demanding scenarios. As health care complexities continue to grow, researchers concur that registered nurses must develop heightened critical thinking capabilities (Li et al., 2019).

In nursing education, a teaching method emerges that aptly aligns with these multifaceted requirements—Case-Based Learning (CBL). CBL fosters active and reflective learning and cultivates critical thinking and practical problem-solving skills (Azizi-Fini et al., 2015). This approach resonates with Bloom's (1956) taxonomy of higher-order cognitive skills, which encompasses analysis, evaluation, and application (Roell, 2019)—among other skills. Within the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction, CBL is a powerful tool. It provides an engaging alternative to traditional teaching methods (Basta, 2017) and is adaptable to different instructional contexts and proficiency levels.

Several studies have explored the effectiveness of case-based learning (CBL) in teaching English in medical, nursing, and specialized contexts. Šelmić (2021) highlighted the significance of CBL in teaching English for medical purposes, integrating language and professional settings effectively. Mamutova and Tursinbaeva (2022) emphasized CBL's role in fostering analytical skills and problem-solving in real-life situations. Yoo and Park (2015) studied nursing students and revealed that case-based learning improved communication, problem-solving, and motivation. Andreassen and Holmsen (2018) described nursing students' positive experiences with CBL, indicating that it effectively combines theory and practice to enhance judgment and critical thinking skills by applying theory in real-life scenarios. These studies showed the potential of CBL to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills in medical, nursing, and specialized education. Additionally, in English language instruction, previous studies (e.g., Dharmayanti, 2021; Nae, 2019; Rantisi, 2021) explored the potential of CBL to enrich language learning through contextualized and engaging methodologies.

Addressing the transition to nursing English classrooms, lecturers play a pivotal role in recognizing students' needs before ESP instruction (Nashir et al., 2022). A nursing faculty lecturer at Syiah Kuala University emphasized the concurrent enhancement of critical thinking and language skills, especially oral communication. According to this dual objective, the lecturer incorporates case-based learning into English for nursing classes. This condition introduces a pivotal question:

- How does the lecturer effectively integrate the CBL approach into the nursing English classroom?

The current study delves into practical implementation, bridging ‘theory with action’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2009, 2023a), and optimizing the interplay between language enhancement and nursing skill development.

2. Background

2.1. Case-based learning

Case-based learning (CBL)—also known as case study teaching or case method learning—has diverse interpretations based on the field and case type. Its origins date back to 1912 when James Lorrain Smith (Sturdy, 2007), the first full-time pathology professor at the University of Edinburgh, introduced the ‘case method of teaching pathology’. This method connects clinical practice with scientific theory by encouraging students to correlate their clinical records with postmortem findings. The approach gained traction at Harvard Business School in 1920 and is still used today (Thistlethwaite et al., 2012).

Hou (2019) asserted that CBL maximizes students’ learning autonomy through ‘self-regulated learning’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2012). Students proactively grasp, organize, and analyze case-related information before class. They lead discussions, share information, exchange ideas, and collaboratively address problems during class. Roell (2019) also emphasized that a case study should focus on a specific situation or problem that is familiar to students. Teachers can create cases or use available online resources to develop cases from coursebooks or current events. These resources—including articles, videos, and tutorials—can be adapted for classroom use.

To be effective, cases presented in class must adhere to standards (Dharmayanti, 2021). The time-intensive nature of (a) case analysis, (b) discussion, (c) reflection, and (d) evaluation necessitates thoughtful consideration of class duration. The cases fall into three categories: (a) scientific research, (b) practical real-world scenarios, and (c) instructional educational activities (Sagimbayeva et al., 2018). Incorporating these categorizations and considerations into the selection and design of cases enriches the case-based learning experience. This allows educators to tailor their approach to the learning goals, needs, and capabilities of their students, thereby fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

2.2. Case-based learning procedure

Because CBL can be used in various ways in the classroom, there are no set stages or protocols for incorporating case-based learning into teaching and learning processes. Experts have suggested various other approaches to adopt case-based learning in classrooms. Roell (2019) proposed a comprehensive six-phase method for effectively implementing case-based language education.

The process begins with an engaging introduction in which the instructor presents a real-life or hypothetical case scenario and introduces relevant vocabulary and key concepts. Subsequently, students delve into reading and analyzing resources related to the case to enhance their critical thinking and language comprehension. The learning experience continues with dynamic group discussions, which foster collaborative exploration and diverse insights. In the presentation and justification phase, students showcase their proposed solutions by drawing on the knowledge they acquired in previous steps to articulate their thoughts coherently. A feedback session follows, which enables constructive peer and instructor critiques, driving continuous improvement. The final step encourages reflection, prompting students to reflect on the connections between the case study, their language learning objectives, and the insights they gained throughout the process. This methodological framework skillfully integrates case-based learning with language acquisition, critical thinking, collaborative skills, and metacognitive awareness—for more on these topics see Foster-Cohen (2009), Hartman, (2013), Jordan, (2012), Nardi (2017), and Salmani Nodoushan (2011).

In addition, according to Hurynovich (2017), case-based learning requires three steps: (a) individual preparation, where students prepare independently by looking up, reading, and analyzing relevant topics; (b) small group discussion, where students participate in the group discussion with the findings of their study; and (c) big group or class discussion, where students share knowledge, exchange ideas, examine problems, and find solutions. Both procedures highlight group discussion as the central activity in case-based learning, where students actively engage in (a) information sharing, (b) idea exchange, (c) problem analysis, and (d) collaborative problem-solving. This interactive approach uses students' communicative and critical thinking skills to enhance their learning experiences.

2.3. Use of case-based learning in nursing education

Case-based learning in nursing education has been the subject of numerous studies by different researchers. An example is a qualitative study conducted by Abou-Zaid (2014) about how “case-based learning” was implemented for undergraduate nursing students. The research conducted at RCSI-Bahrain's nursing faculty highlights the significance of Case-Based Learning (CBL) as a crucial element in improving information and knowledge delivery. This study emphasizes a shift toward innovative teaching methods, highlighting the adoption and benefits of CBL. Students clearly preferred CBL over traditional lectures because of its interactive and engaging nature. Additionally, the research highlighted the potential of CBL in smaller group settings, recognizing it as a catalyst for enhancing student engagement and understanding. The aim of this study is to extend the use of case-based activity sessions, reinforcing the

pivotal role of CBL in the learning process for nursing students across various academic years.

Forsgren et al. (2014) conducted a study to evaluate the case method in nursing education. They mentioned that Case-Based Learning (CBL) is a dynamic educational approach that immerses students in cognitive challenges linked to real-life situations. This study explored nursing students' perceptions of CBL as a tool for supporting their learning. By employing qualitative content analysis on nursing students' course evaluations, the study found that students perceived CBL as an effective fusion of theory and practice, offering a glimpse into their future profession. The approach enabled students to comprehensively understand patient care by bridging theoretical knowledge with real-life scenarios. Reflections during case seminars broadened students' perspectives, enhanced cooperation skills, and facilitated lasting knowledge retention. CBL enables nursing students to hone their critical thinking and judgment by applying theoretical ideas in real-world situations. This method provides students with fundamental knowledge of patient care, enabling them to behave professionally in their future roles and ultimately improve patient care.

Another investigation into case-based learning in nursing education was carried out by Yoo and Park (2015). Their study examined how second-year nursing students' problem-solving, communication, and learning motivation were affected by case-based learning. The experimental and control groups using case-based learning and conventional lecture-based learning were compared in this study. The goal of this study was to ascertain how well case-based learning helps nursing students develop these crucial abilities and motivations. The results supported the effectiveness of case-based learning as a valuable educational strategy in nursing education by showing significant improvements in communication, problem-solving, and motivation skills.

Likewise, another study by Qi et al. (2018) discussed the use of case-based learning to teach clinical skills to nursing undergraduates. The purpose of this study was to assess the effectiveness of case-based learning (CBL) in developing practical skills among undergraduate nursing students. The experimental group included 147 nursing interns, and the control group consisted of 71 interns. While the control group received conventional instruction, the experimental group received CBL instructions. The experimental group outperformed the control group in all categories, namely, (a) overall performance, (b) practical skills, (c) fundamental knowledge, (d) problem-solving ability, (e) communication ability, and (f) professional attitudes. Additionally, the experimental group outperformed the control group in terms of critical thinking ability. CBL was found to be a useful strategy for enhancing nursing students' practical knowledge and critical thinking.

Additionally, Andreassen and Holmsen (2018) studied case-based learning in nursing education. This study examined the effects of case-based learning, a pedagogical technique used in nursing education. This approach is claimed to close a gap in nursing education that affects how well-prepared nurses are for different roles, especially in critical thinking. Using a cross-sectional design, the study investigated students' perceptions of case-based learning, placing particular emphasis on its role in combining theoretical knowledge with real-world applications. This study emphasized how case-based learning provides nursing students with a useful platform for improving their critical thinking and decision-making skills by applying theoretical concepts to real-world situations. It is emphasized that teachers and students work together to solve problems, and teachers' involvement and engagement were seen as crucial components. This study recommended case-based learning as an effective method for promoting critical thinking, especially when used in conjunction with other pedagogical techniques.

2.4. Needs analysis of teaching English to nursing students

In the new post-colonial era and specifically after World War II, English has become the preferred 'lingua franca' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024) and is used for intercommunication in both public and professional settings. Although native varieties of English have given in to 'world Englishes', and native speakers are no longer 'points of reference', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023b), intelligible communication is always mandatory, and even more so in nurse talk. Being one of the 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021), of English for specific purposes, 'English for nursing' has, nevertheless, recently emerged as a distinct specialization within the realm of ESP.

This specialization focuses on nurses' unique English language usage patterns, which differ from those of doctors, health care professionals, and paraprofessionals in both clinical settings and nursing education (Bosher, 2012). The evolution of this field saw the progression from English for Medical Purposes (EMP) to English for Nursing Purposes (ENP), tailoring English courses to the 'specific needs' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020) of clinical nurses and nursing students. Consequently, ENP teaching must consider critical aspects such as learner characteristics, content scope, language application, and suitable course types.

Febriyanti (2018) emphasized the increased complexity of English for nursing because of its integration with medical terminology, which may need to be more comprehensible. Nursing-related vocabulary (or 'register') presents intricate variations and meanings, demanding specialized comprehension, particularly in practical contexts. Addressing these challenges requires an approach centered on English for Specific Purposes (ESP), which addresses

students' distinct needs to achieve efficient and effective learning outcomes. While a high level of English proficiency is not a prerequisite for ESP programs, learners are expected to use English as a medium for learning (Javid, 2015). A customized teaching approach is indispensable because each learner possesses individual aspirations and objectives that impact their learning achievements.

Needs analysis, as proposed by Basturkmen (2010) and Salmani Nodoushan (2020), emerges as a crucial phase for educators undertaking ESP (see also Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). This stage identifies learners' language requirements and specific skills required by their domain of study. This process empowers ESP instructors to gather comprehensive information about learners' needs and facilitates targeted and successful teaching strategies.

In a recent study (Faidah, 2022) exploring the need for ESP among nursing students, a strong demand for tailored English materials and classes aligned with their professional requirements was evident. The participants prioritized refining their speaking and listening abilities as their primary goals. Although reading and writing were considered unimportant, incorporating reading and writing activities into the ESP curriculum was beneficial for enhancing all language skills. These findings align with Wulandari et al.'s (2019) research, affirming that nursing students predominantly seek enhanced speaking and listening skills for effective English communication. In summary, Faidah's (2022) research, supported by Wulandari et al. (2019), underpinned the robust demand for specialized English materials and classes among nursing students, emphasizing honing speaking and listening skills for proficient English communication.

3. Method

A qualitative research methodology was employed to explore the implementation of the Case-Based Learning (CBL) method in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction within the Nursing Faculty of Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh. This approach enabled an in-depth understanding of the participants' experiences and perspectives (cf. Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.1. Participants

The study was conducted by the Nursing Faculty, Universitas Syiah Kuala, which is recognized for its nursing education in Aceh. The capacity of the faculty to conduct CBL sessions, particularly in small tutorial classes, facilitated the implementation of the study. The participants included one lecturer and a class of 15 students. Purposeful sampling ensured that the individuals sampled for the study meet specific criteria.

The lecturer was chosen based on her (a) English proficiency (minimum TOEFL score of 500), (b) teaching experience in English and nursing courses, and (c) participation in a CBL workshop. The students were selected based on intermediate-level English proficiency and successful completion of a fundamental nursing course.

3.2. Materials

Data were collected through multiple methods to comprehensively explore CBL implementation in the nursing English classroom. The observation sheet consisting of statements that describe the steps of learning using the case-based method proposed by Roell (2019) was used as a guide for classroom observation. The researchers observed ten class sessions by adopting a non-participant role. This approach facilitated the observation of both the lecturer's activities and the students' interactions. Moreover, documentation played an important role as an instrument in this study. Documents such as lesson plans and modules were analyzed collaboratively by the lecturer and the instructional team. These documents aligned with the objectives of a nursing English course.

3.3. Procedure

After going through the administration process to conduct this research, the researchers collected the data using the non-participant observation method. The researchers sat in the corner of the room to observe the teaching and learning process. While observing, the researchers filled in the observation sheet that had been provided for them previously, and they wrote things related to the object of this research using pen, paper; they also used their cellphone cameras to record videos and take pictures. The observations were made for approximately 10 meetings. Each meeting took approximately 3 hours to complete—from 08:30 to 11:30 am. The researchers arrived earlier at the class to set up the camera and chair before the lecturer arrived. Then, to strengthen the research on this case-based learning method, the researchers analyzed documents given by the lecturer—such as the module, lesson plan, rubric of assessment, and students' scores.

Following the collection of all data from the document analysis and classroom observation, a qualitative technique was used for data analysis. For the first step, the researchers conducted data condensation through transcribing the observations and interview results regarding the implementation of CBL in the classroom. This process involved reducing the data volume while preserving the critical and pertinent information required to address the research questions. The second critical stage of the analysis process was data presentation, which is also referred to as data display. During this phase, the

researchers organized the data into distinct categories, themes, and patterns and used a variety of visual aids such as charts, tables, diagrams, and matrices to effectively present the data. The third critical aspect of qualitative data analysis is drawing and validating conclusions. During this phase, the researchers interpreted the data to discern emerging patterns, relationships, themes, and categories. Subsequently, conclusions were drawn based on this interpretation of the data. These conclusions were then verified by referencing the data to ensure that they were substantiated by the evidence.

4. Results

The results revealed that the lecturer implemented the case-based learning approach in multiple phases. During each phase, the lecturer incorporated unique techniques to achieve the learning goals. Her procedure included six consecutive steps:

- Step 1: Case preparation and introduction
- Step 2: Reading and analyzing materials
- Step 3: Group discussion
- Step 4: Presentation and justification
- Step 5: Feedback session
- Step 6: Reflection

Step 1: Case preparation and introduction

Based on the researchers' observation, at the beginning of the case-based learning class, the lecturer created a welcoming atmosphere. She greeted the students warmly and called the roll to ensure that all students were present. After the roll call, she shared the learning objectives for the day, clearly outlining what the students would learn, and what they were expected to achieve during the class.

To set the language learning context and encourage English language use, the lecturer reminded the students that, for the duration of the English class, they were expected to communicate only in English, and every word that was uttered by the students would receive a remark from her. This language immersion approach aims to create an English-speaking environment that enhances students' language proficiency and confidence.

Subsequently, the lecturer introduced the central focus of the day's learning activities: a specific case that the students would discuss. The lecturer prepared the case days before the meeting. This case was carefully chosen to align with the learning objectives and challenge the students' critical thinking and language skills.

Based on the data from the lesson plan, the researchers knew that the main objectives of this course were (a) to develop a good understanding of the nursing process and (b) to apply English to the nursing process. Therefore, the topics that have been discussed in this class were mainly about the basic nursing process; patient admission, patient assessment, nursing diagnosis, nursing implementation, discharge planning, home visits, and medication. The cases given were five cases with different levels of difficulty—for the topic of patient assessment, nursing diagnosis, and nursing implementation were using the same case. Then, in this phase, the lecturer also conveyed the activity that the students would undertake after understanding the case given—that is, compiling a role play. To promote language learning during the case-based learning (CBL) session, the lecturer devised an engaging activity to assess the students' speaking and pronunciation fluency. Each student was asked to read the case aloud. Reading aloud provided an opportunity for the lecturer to evaluate their verbal communication skills. While the students read the case, the lecturer attentively noted any mispronounced vocabulary item. This activity not only served as an assessment but also as a teaching moment.

After the students had finished reading, the lecturer transformed the experience into a valuable language-learning opportunity. She wrote down the identified vocabulary items on the whiteboard, invited the students to repeat them, and guided them to correct their mispronunciations to improve their speaking skills. She also allowed the students to use an online dictionary on their smartphone to look up the meanings of the words and correct their pronunciation. This integrated approach allowed students to engage actively in language learning, explore case scenarios, and foster cohesive and effective learning experiences. In a consistent teaching pattern observed throughout the meetings, the lecturer skillfully introduced case studies, engaged the students in focused reading to improve pronunciation, and guided them through in-depth problem analysis. This introductory activity lasted for an average of 15-20 minutes per meeting.

Step 2: Reading and analyzing materials

In the second step of case-based learning (CBL), the lecturer provided the students with valuable opportunities to engage with related materials depending on the specific case. For patient admission, nursing diagnoses, and home visits, the lecturer began by explaining the relevant theory or concept to the students. She provided materials in the form of presentations, videos, and documents from online resources.

In the patient admission case, the lecturer not only delivered a concept explanation but also provided some examples of expressions that can be used to receive patients in the hospital. In the case of nursing diagnoses, despite the

theory from the nursing diagnoses book, the lecturer explained a video from an online resource and provided an example of a nursing report that was used internationally. In the home visit case, the lecturer prepared a complete presentation slide about the concept and theory of home visit and explained it to the students. This theoretical foundation equipped them with the necessary knowledge before proceeding to the case analysis.

Additionally, in other cases (i.e., patient assessment and discharge planning), the lecturer assigned readings from the prepared modules and provided the students with a self-guided exploration of the theory at home. Students were also allowed to read from other sources to enhance their knowledge of the concepts of patient assessment and discharge planning. By integrating theory into the session, the lecturer aimed to enhance students' comprehension and understanding of the case scenario, providing them with the necessary knowledge to tackle the challenges presented.

In the case analysis process, the lecturer re-read the case while explaining the problems in the case. She directed the students to analyze the cases by paying attention to every piece of data in the narrative of the case, such as who the patient was, what disease he was suffering from, what examinations had been carried out, what stages of treatment the patient had received, and what follow-up plans were to be carried out for this patient. There were two cases (discharge planning and medication) that were accompanied by a set of thought-provoking questions, while other cases were only provided by a task or activity that students should undertake after solving the case—namely, compiling a role play dialog. These questions serve as essential guiding prompts to assist students in their case analysis. During this step, students were required to thoroughly read and comprehend the case materials and then systematically address all the questions. Students were enthusiastic to listen to their lecturer's explanation about the case. The reading and analysis activities were performed for approximately 10 minutes.

Step 3: Group discussion

Moving on to the next stage of case-based learning (CBL), the focus turns toward group discussions, encouraging collaborative problem-solving, and facilitating knowledge sharing among students. During this phase of case-based learning, the instructor divided the class into pairs, and the students engaged in discussing the cases. These pairs change daily, providing each student with the opportunity to converse with a different peer each day.

During the group discussion, the lecturer allocated approximately 20 minutes, allowing ample time for students to explore the case thoroughly and exchange ideas. In this interactive session, the lecturer actively accompanies the students, providing guidance and clarification as necessary. The students were

encouraged to ask questions, and the lecturer responded by using a combination of English and Indonesian to facilitate their comprehension (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016). In this inclusive learning environment, students felt comfortable using their mother tongue to communicate with their peers. However, when interacting with the lecturer, they predominantly used English, practiced their language skills, and built confidence in effectively expressing themselves.

In questions, students engaged in discussions to address each question. Conversely, in cases lacking explicit questions, students sustained the dialog by crafting relevant role-play interactions tailored to the given case. This interactive exercise involved one student adopting the role of a nurse, while another embodied that of a patient. This role-play dialog preparation was consistently implemented in all cases.

Step 4: Presentation and justification

Moving on to the next step of case-based learning (CBL), the focus shifts to presentation and justification, where students have the opportunity to showcase their findings and insights. To ensure fairness, the lecturer randomly assigned groups to present their answers to the class, allowing everyone a chance to actively participate. During the presentations, students eagerly shared their responses and attempted to use English despite occasional errors. As they presented, the lecturer actively listened to and provided direct corrections for any pronunciation errors. This immediate 'corrective feedback' prompted students to momentarily pause, correct their errors, and confidently continue to speak.

The justification step in case-based learning (CBL) involves students presenting their answers and reasoning to the class. During the class observations, it was evident that the lecturer took a proactive approach in this step. As each group presented their answers, the researchers attentively listened to their justifications and engaged in constructive discussions.

Throughout the presentations, the lecturer provided positive reinforcement by rewarding students with encouraging phrases like "good," "well done," or "excellent." This form of appreciation enhances students' confidence and motivates them to further engage in English communication.

Because only two cases were provided by questions, presentation was not the core of this stage. The main activity in this step was presenting role play because the focus was not only on the students' critical thinking skills to solve problems but also on enhancing their language ability. This role play was always performed after presenting the case solution, unless the case required a long discussion, such as in the case of nursing diagnoses. Then, the role play

was conducted on the next day. The lecturer randomly selected groups without volunteers. Students enthusiastically performed their role plays. As they performed, the lecturer watched closely and took notes on their performance, particularly noting any common mistakes in pronunciation and accuracy.

Step 5: Feedback session

During the feedback step, the lecturer initiated a constructive discussion by first asking students to share their opinions on their peers' presentations and role-play performances. This collaborative approach encouraged students to actively engage with each other's work and provide valuable feedback. After gathering the students' perspectives, the lecturer provided feedback and insightful comments on the strengths of each group's performance and identified areas for improvement. To help students understand their errors better, the lecturer explained the correct forms and language usage on the whiteboard. The feedback process occurred after each group presented their role play, ensuring that each team received personalized guidance and support.

Step 6: Reflection

During the reflection phase, the lecturer engaged the students in a thoughtful discussion of their learning experiences. She first inquired about the students' feelings, and many students expressed their happiness in learning English during this class. Next, the lecturer asked the students about their response to today's class, specifically, whether they had learned anything new or not. Some students eagerly shared their insights, expressing the knowledge they had gained and the valuable language skills they had developed through their various activities. However, some students preferred to listen to and absorb the perspectives of their peers.

At this stage, the panel also engaged in a discussion of the students' performance during the role play, considering their decisions and actions. This afforded the students the opportunity to share their thoughts and experiences regarding their participation in the role play. The lecturer not only provided constructive feedback on the students' performances, highlighting areas of strength and areas for improvement but also took the opportunity to motivate and encourage the students to continue speaking English and take pride in their language skills. The lecturer emphasized the importance of using English as a means of effective communication in the nursing profession and beyond, fostering a positive and supportive learning environment. Moreover, this phase also presented an opportunity for students to offer suggestions for enhancing the case study and proposing potential adaptations and/or improvements.

5. Discussion

As outlined in previous sections, this investigation focuses on the application of case-based learning (CBL) for English instruction at Universitas Syiah Kuala. Specifically, the researchers explored the systematics used by the lecturer in implementing CBL, based on the concepts proposed by Roell (2019) and the assessments conducted. The study also analyzes the results of students' speaking performance using this method. Using observation, interviews, and document analysis, this discussion provides a comprehensive understanding of the application of CBL in teaching English.

The study reveals several aspects that make CBL adaptable to language classes. One finding is the lecturer's ability to create case scenarios aligned with (a) students' background knowledge, (b) critical thinking skills, and (c) English proficiency. This approach helps students connect theoretical concepts with practical understanding, enhancing their learning experience. Saleewong et al. (2012) noted that case-based learning aims to create cases and stories that influence behavior and attitudes, stimulating discussion and debate (Zak, 2013). This approach helps students express their ideas more effectively when solving cases.

CBL, typically used in non-linguistic fields, can also be applied to language learning. Basta (2017) noted that this method is applicable across disciplines, and Saleewong et al. (2012) reported that 45% of case methods are used in medical disciplines, including nursing. In this connection, our observations indicate that the lecturer effectively applied the case-based method in nursing English classes due to her strong background in both linguistics and nursing. Her proficiency in English and extensive teaching experience in nursing provide an advantage for teaching English for specific purposes using CBL. This observation lends support to Roell's (2019) claims that language teachers must be familiar with the topic discussed in case studies, or collaborate with experts to create relevant cases.

The case-based approach effectively engages students in verbal interactions, especially in discussions (Roell, 2019). In this connection, the lecturer enforced a rule for students to speak only in English during lessons, which helped improve their speaking skills (cf. Kaniadewi & Sriyanto, 2019). However, during group discussions, the lecturer mixed Indonesian and English to prevent misunderstandings—and to provide L1-mediated 'scaffolding' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016). Balancing the use of the first language and English is crucial, with the main goal being to foster an English-focused environment for better communication.

In implementing the case-based method, the lecturer integrated language learning into CBL—which is a form of 'content-and-language' integration (cf. Breeze & Azparren Legarre, 2021; Francomacaro, 2019; Naddeo, 2019;

Salmani Nodoushan, 2020). Instead of introducing vocabulary as suggested by Roell (2019), the lecturer had students read cases aloud. This practice allowed her to identify and address pronunciation errors. According to Kelly (2000), reading aloud explores spelling and pronunciation connections, and Huang (2010) supported this by noting its benefits for pronunciation practice.

The lecturer used various materials, including presentations, videos, and documents, during the reading and analysis steps. This aligns with Basta (2017), who noted that case-based learning involves providing crucial problem details and context through visuals. Roell (2019) supported this by emphasizing the need for essential understanding before case studies. The lecturer also included thought-provoking questions to stimulate discussion and problem-solving, aligning with Nae (2019) who noted that case tasks prompt discussions and decision-making.

During group discussions, the lecturer guided students, offered clarification, and facilitated interactions. Despite the challenges noted by Esteban and Canado (cited in Nae, 2019), the lecturer's extensive knowledge of both languages and nursing ensured effective facilitation. The lecturer encouraged active participation, deep questioning, and critical thinking, allowing students to use a mix of Indonesian and English to achieve correct understanding.

In the presentation and justification phase, role plays were a key activity. Nae (2019) and Roell (2019) highlighted role-play as a motivational tool and a means to immerse students in the case environment. This approach allowed students to practice language skills and politeness (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2019) in various roles.

During the feedback session, the lecturer used peer feedback constructively, allowing students to express and refine their thoughts while considering diverse perspectives (cf. Ching, 2014). The lecturer reviewed and corrected language usage on the whiteboard.

In the reflection phase, students were encouraged to offer suggestions for improving the case study, as suggested by Roell (2019). The lecturer sought students' feedback on the CBL experience to enhance future teaching. Overall, the reflection stage of CBL involves motivating students to reflect on their learning experiences, evaluate progress, and identify improvements. Teachers' encouragement and constructive feedback (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010) foster a positive attitude toward learning, motivating students to achieve better results and supporting their personal development.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study explored the dynamic implementation of case-based learning (CBL) in nursing education. Through close observation of the

lecturer's tutorial class, the student gained insight into the step-by-step process. The introduction phase of CBL established an English-immersive environment, presenting compelling case scenarios. The reading and analysis stages nurtured critical thinking through multimedia resources and thought-provoking questions. The subsequent group discussion phase highlighted the lecturer's facilitator role, promoting English practice and peer collaboration. The presentation and justification steps revealed the significance of role-play in merging language skills and nursing contexts. Lastly, the feedback and reflection stage demonstrated the lecturer's adept use of peer feedback to enhance language proficiency and student engagement.

This investigation illuminated the potential of CBL in nurturing (a) language skills, (b) critical thinking, and (c) nursing abilities. As education evolves, further exploration of innovative techniques like CBL is recommended to effectively prepare nursing professionals for their future roles. In future research, it would be valuable to examine the long-term impact of CBL on nursing practice and language proficiency in students. Additionally, investigating the challenges and opportunities in implementing CBL in different nursing education contexts could provide valuable insights for educators. Moreover, exploring ways to integrate technology and online resources into CBL could enhance its effectiveness in language and nursing skill development.

Authors' Statement

Siti Mutia Cayarani contributed to sections 1, 3, 4 and 5 and Dohra Fitriisia worked on section 4. Asnawi worked on sections 5 and 6, and Khwanchit Suwannopparat contributed on section 2 of the article.

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